

Appraising Vocational and Entrepreneurial Skills Acquisition Programmes Impact on Local Technological Revolution in Ondo State, Nigeria.

Erinsakin, Obafemi

Rufus Giwa Polytechnic,

Department of Business Administration and Management, Ondo, Ondo State Nigeria

&

Agun, Paulinah Olusola

Adeyemi Federal University of Education,

Department of Adult and Continuing Education, Ondo, Ondo State Nigeria

&

Akinbebije, John

Adeyemi Federal University of Education,

Department of Adult and Continuing Education, Ondo, Ondo State Nigeria

Abstract

The implementation of vocational and entrepreneurial skills acquisition programme by Ondo State Government is to tackle poverty, unemployment and technological backwardness of the state among others. Thus, necessitated the study. Descriptive survey research decision was used. The population of the study comprised the present participants and graduate of vocational and entrepreneurial skills acquisition programme (VESAA). The sample size of the study was 1,080 responsibility selected through a multi-purpose sampling technique. Two research questions and one research hypothesis were raised and formulated for the study. Data were obtained through a self-structured research instruments by the researchers tagged "questionnaire on appraising vocational and entrepreneurial skill acquisition programmes impact on local technological revolution in Ondo state, Nigeria". It was fashioned on 4-point likert rating scale and rated on 4 point; 4, 3, 2 and 1, of Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Disagreed (D) and Strongly Disagreed (SD), respectively. The research instruments were validated by two experts in measurement and evaluation while, the research instruments reliability was done through test-retest method at two weeks interval and 0.74 was got as co-efficient reliability. Data got on the research questions were analyzed through descriptive statistics (simple percentages, frequency counted and mean (\bar{X}) while, data obtained on research hypothesis were analyzed using inferential statistics (Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient PPMCC). Based on the results of the study conclusions were made that VESAP could promote local technology. Recommendations were made therefore premised on the conclusion that, more centres of VESAP should be established, public should be sensitized through the print and electronic media, and host.

Keywords: Appraising, Vocational, Entrepreneurial, Skill Acquisition, Local Technology, Revolution.

Background to the study

One of the factors that confirmed and categorized Nigeria as a developing nation is technological backwardness of the country. Nigeria 21st country is skill relying on the developed nations or has term world for survival, technologically. Technologically, the country is technologically lagging behind thus, retarding the country's development in multi-dimensional to development and progress in virtually all the sectors of the economy (agriculture, medicine, education, medicine, commerce, transportation, communication, and host of others).

The technological retrogression of the country is a serious challenge to Nigeria as a nation considering the present global drive towards technological advanced society. Eke, Igwesi and Orji (2011), stated that Nigeria technological status calls for the need to improve the country technologically for a sustainable development in a holistic context.

According to Agagu (2007)

Real development involves capacity and increase capacity of the people to transform effectively national resources into good and practical application of their creative talents and productive labourforce, hence, technology and entrepreneurship education are the bedrocks for national development and roadmaps for achieving the vision 2020 for Nigeria pg;98.

Further, Agagu (2007) strongly maintain that for the nation, Nigeria to achieve the national goal of vision 2020, there should be a total restructuring and integration of skill based educational system into the educational curriculum for self-reliance, capacity building and technological advancement of the country, the implication of this that there is a dire need to reposition educational curriculum on programmes that will give people practical and functional vocational and entrepreneurial skills for economic and technological prosperity of the country.

Nwogu (1988), noted that the worth and might of any nation is determined by the level of her technological sophistication. In Nigeria, my scholars or academics have observed the position of formal system of education. In Nigeria, my scholars or academics have observed the position of formal system of education and technological advancement as a target area that needs to be improved. Erinsakin (2014), observed that formal system of education and may not be able or capable to equip people with the desirable vocational skills so that the technological sector of the country could be improved the realization of this fact, however, informs the development and invigoration of various skills acquisition programmes on different vocations and entrepreneurial activities in order to improve the economy and technological base of the country. Ezeyi and Okone (1999), stresses that skills acquisition is vital to the national growth and development of any nation economically and technologically. Nigeria social and economic will be drastically be improved it, practical vocational skills are giving to the people. Gbamari (2011), affirmed that skills development has been man's means of materials transformation from the earliest time.

The federal republic of Nigeria (FRN) (2004), stressed that giving the necessary vocational skills to the people would lead to the production of craft man, technicians and skilled

personnel which could result into enterprising and self-reliant and bring development in the technological sector of the country. Collaborating this, Nwamaka and Amachile (2011) contended that effective training in skill acquisition had increasingly contributed to the technical excellence and economic self-reliance of industrialized nations the recognition of the above facts spurred government at all levels to synergize efforts with some international agencies towards articulations as sustainable skill acquisition programmes in different vocations for economic self-reliance, poverty eradication. Unemployment reduction and enable people to be capable of making use of local materials for local technology. In this endeavor, Ondo State Government (ODSG) is not left behind.

Ondo State Government therefore took the initiative to implement vocational and entrepreneurial skills acquiring programmes to tackle poverty, unemployment with their antecedent socio-economic challenges in the state. Also, to promote the adoption of local technology by giving people the practical skills for such. Hence the programmes in Ondo State, by the edict that established them put the vocational skill acquisition programme under the Ministry of Adult Education, Technical and Vocational Education while, entrepreneurial skill acquisition is being run by the Ministry of Commerce and Industry in the unit of Investments and Establishment.

The Ondo State Vocational and Entrepreneurial Skills Acquisition Programmes have been good topics of research to the researchers. Several studies had been conducted on area of influence of Vocational and Entrepreneurial Skills Acquisition Programme on poverty eradication, unemployment reduction, small size enterprise promotion and development, and hosts. Observably, none seems to have been done on Vocational and Entrepreneurial Skills Acquisition programmes of Ondo State Nigeria on local technological revolution in the 21st century. This identified gap thus, motivated the researchers to carry out the study.

Statement of the problem

The vocational and entrepreneurial skills acquisition programmes of Ondo State government in Nigeria were strategically implemented to reduce poverty and unemployment and engendered people with vibrant, practical and marketable skills in different vocations and entrepreneurial activities for the promotion and revolution of local technology.

The researchers were therefore, interested to appraise these programmes particularly on its impacts on local technological revolution the 21st century in Ondo State, Nigeria. It was against this background the study was carried out.

Objective of the study

The major objective of the study was to appraise vocational and entrepreneurial skill acquisition programme impact on local technology revolution in the 21st century in Ondo State, Nigeria. The specific Objectives were to:

1. determine the impact of vocational and entrepreneurial skills acquisition programme on equipping people with skill for promotion of local technology in Ondo State, Nigeria.

- ascertain the composite influence of vocational and entrepreneurial skills acquisition programme on local technological practices in Ondo state, Nigeria.

Researcher questions

- Vocational Skills Acquisition Programme equip people with skills to promote local technology in Ondo State, Nigeria?
- Can Entrepreneurial Skills Acquisition Programme enhance people with skills for local technological development in Ondo State, Nigeria?

Research Hypothesis

- H₀₁:** There will be no significant relationship between Vocational And Entrepreneurial Skills Acquisition Programme and local technology promotion in Ondo State, Nigeria.

Significance for the study

The following were the significance of the study;

The findings of the study will enable governments to know the impact of vocational and entrepreneurial skills acquisition programmes on local technological promotion.

The results of the researcher will also enable public to know that through the programmes could acquire and entrepreneurial skills for local technology practices.

The study will as to the existing literature on vocational and entrepreneurial skills acquisition programmes thus, serve as source of reference to researchers in future.

Conceptual Framework

Vocational Skill Acquisition (VSK)

Erinsakin (2014), stressed that vocational skill acquisition is due of the areas of focus of governments of nations of the world. VSK is acquiring skills in different vocations that could strengthen individuals' capacity and ability to perform vocational tasks on activities (Erinsakin 2014, PG 48). Okron (2010) posited that USA is having skills which individuals can use to raise capacity to generate better income for an improved standard of life and sustainable livelihood. Further, that through USA economy of a nation can be repositioned, re-designed, revamped and strengthened. The acquisition of practical skills in various vocations has been found to be very appropriate at addressing some tropical issues such as poverty, unemployment and other socio-economic challenges affecting individuals and nations, particularly the developing commitments like, Nigeria. USA offers skills in the following vocations; food processing, block laying and concreting, welding, oil processing, wood work metal fabrication, plumbing, cloth weaving, chalk making, and hosts.

Uwanieye (2011), asserted that USA would make people to acquire technological literacy which could make them capable of effecting a level of control on their environment. Also, that VSK could train manpower for various works demands, upgrade and update skills for job productivity. Realizing the importance of USA to individuals' and nations' Development economically and technologically, countries of the world like the United States of America,

Germany, Japan, China, Britain and other nations, Nigeria, inclusive have been investing heavily on USA development.

Entrepreneurial Skill Acquisition (ESA)

ESA is one of the innovate and strategic plans to tackle socio-economic challenges such as; poverty and unemployment with their antecedent challenges. Matammi and Awodun (2005), specifically stated a nation Nigeria could only overcome her high level of poverty and unemployment acquisition of skills in entrepreneurship.

Ogundele (2000), stated that ESA is a structured formal conveyance of entrepreneurial competencies which in turns refers to concepts, skills and mental awareness used by individuals during the process of starting and developing their growth oriented ventures. ESA is not just a theoretical measures or approach rather a practical developmental action to tackle poverty and unemployment and develop nations' economy. Salami (2011), opined that the high rate of unemployment and poverty is the disconnection between skill acquisition and entrepreneurship.

Benchard and Toulouso (1998), posited that ESA entails a collection of formalized training and teaching which informs, educates everyone that is interested in business creation on small business management. Erinsakin (2014), stated that the communicative effort of ESA would be evidenced in innovation and creativity, feasibility study, business planning, financial planning, start-up capital, record keeping, costing, forms of business, personal entrepreneurial attributes, time management, accident prevention and safety at work place.

In a summary, the implementation of ESA in Nigeria is the desire and commitment of government to tackle poverty and unemployment, improved economic status of individuals and the country, economic stimulate and priming individuals' mindsets toward business creation, improve one's income generating capacity and wealth creation and hosts.

Theoretical Framework

Becker's Human Capital Theory (BHCT)

The study is anchored on Beckers' Human Capital Theory (BHCT) considered appropriate and relevant to the study. BHCT was propounded by Adam Smith who defined it as the acquired and useful abilities of all the inhabitants and members of a society. Adam Smith stated that through education study and apprenticeship competencies and skills can be acquired to carry out certain operations.

Becker (1993 and 1996), explained Human Capital Theory (HCT) as activity that promotes or increases future consumption and abilities by increasing the resources in people through training. HCT thus, suggests that training or education raises the productivity of workers by imparting useful knowledge and skills that can raise workers' future incomes by increasing their life-time earnings' what seems to be the central idea of Human Capital Theory according to Becker (1993), (1994) and (1996) is that, training is an investment in human capital which in turn results into a high occupational performance of workers.

Becker’s Human Capital Theory further stated that workers’ productivity is determined through acquisition of vocational skill that can be acquired through training. Becker’s critiques offer different explanations on how education is related to workers’ productivity and that higher earnings of educated workers depend on the superior training acquired during the process education, rather than through skills and knowledge.

The appropriateness and relevance of BHCT to the study is presented on the fact that Vocational and Entrepreneurial skills acquisition programmes main goals are to equip people with practical skills for job productivity and enable people to take initiative to earn better incomes. In the context of this study, acquisition of skills in different vocations and entrepreneurship could enhance local technology adoption and practices.

Methodology

Descriptive survey research design will be adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised, two categories of vocational and Entrepreneurial Skills Acquisition programmes in Ondo State, Nigeria. The categories were the current trainees of the programmes which constituted 1,527 and the graduands of the programmes which constituted 4, 736 thus, making the population of the study to be 6,263.

The sample size of the study was 1,080 participants chosen from the actual population of 6,262, thus represent 17% of the entire population of the study. a multi-stage sampling technique was adopted for the study.

Stage I: A purposive sampling technique was used to select a vocational and entrepreneurial skills acquisition programme centres in each of the 18 Local Government Areas of Ondo State.

Stage II: Stratified and proportional sampling techniques were adopted to select 17% of the participants of the programmes comprising the current trainees and graduands at each of the programme centres.

Stage III: Purposive snow-balling sample and proportional sampling technique were used to select 17% of the sample for the study

Population and Sample Chosen from the Local Government Areas of Vocational and Entrepreneurial Skills Programme (VESAP) in Ondo State, Nigeria.

S/N	Names of Local Government Areas in Ondo State	Locations	Current Trainees		Graduands of the Centre		Total Population of current trainees and graduands	Total Sample chosen from the current trainees and graduands/percentages
			Population	Sample Chosen	Population	Sample Chosen		
1	Akoko-North East Local Govt. Centre for (SAEDTP)	Ikare	80	40(32%)	160	20(13%)	240	60(25%)

2	Akoko North West Local Govt. Centre for (SAEDTP)	OkeAgbe	96	40(38%)	186	20(37%)	282	60(21.2%)
3	Akoko South East Local Govt. Centre for (SAEDTP)	Isua	78	40(31%)	246	20(49%)	324	60(19%)
4	Akoko South West Local Govt. Centre for (SAEDTP)	Oka	80	40(32%)	264	20(53%)	344	60(17.4%)
5	Akure North Local Govt. Centre for (SAEDTP)	Iju/Itaogbolu	88	40(35%)	326	20(65%)	414	60(17.4%)
6	Akure South Local Govt. Centre for (SAEDTP)	Akure	96	40(38%)	210	20(42%)	306	60(20%)
7	Ese-Odo Local Govt. Centre for (SAEDTP)	Igbekebo	64	40(27%)	338	20(68%)	402	60(15%)
8	Idanre Local Govt. Centre for (SAEDTP)	Owena	78	40(31%)	256	20(51%)	234	60(18%)
9	Ifedore Local Govt. Centre for (SAEDTP)	Igbara-Oke	86	40(34%)	210	20(42%)	296	60(20.2%)
10	Ile-Oluji/OkeIgbo Local Govt. Centre for (SAEDTP)	Ile-Oluji	50	40(20%)	198	20(40%)	248	60(24.1%)
11	Ilaje Local Govt. Centre for (SAEDTP)	Igbokoda	94	40(38%)	284	20(57%)	383	60(21.2%)
12	Irele Local Govt. Centre	Ode-Irele	100	40(40%)	486	20(97%)	586	60(10.2%)

	for (SAEDTP)							
13	Odigbo Local Govt. Centre for (SAEDTP)	Ore	68	40(27%)	234	20(47%)	302	60(20%)
14	Okitipupa Local Govt. Centre for (SAEDTP)	Okitipupa	78	40(31%)	312	20(62%)	390	60(15.3%)
15	Ondo East Local Govt. Centre for (SAEDTP)	Bolorunduro	65	40(26%)	288	20(58%)	353	60(16.9%)
16	Ondo West Local Govt. Centre for (SAEDTP)	Ondo	126	40(50%)	219	20(44%)	345	60(17.3%)
17	Ose Local Govt. Centre for (SAEDTP)	Ifon	102	40(41%)	300	20(60%)	402	60(15%)
18	Owo Local	Owo	98	40(39%)	214	20(43%)	312	60(19.2%)
	Total		1,527		4,736		6,263	1,080(17.2%)

Source: Field Study, 2024

The data collected for the study was done through a research instrument self-developed by the researcher and tagged, “Questionnaire on Vocational and Entrepreneurial Skills Acquisition Programmes Impact on Local Technological Revolution in the 21st Century in Ondo State, Nigeria” fashioned on a four-point likert – like option scale of Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Disagreed (D) and Strongly Disagreed SD). Responses on the scale were rated and scored on 4, 3, 2 and 1 for SA, A, D and SD, respectively.

The research instruments were validated by two experts in Test and Measurement while its reliability was determined through test-retest method at two weeks interval. 0.74 coefficient reliability was obtained, thus, made the researchers to adjudge the research instrument to be good enough for the study. Descriptive statistics (simple percentages, frequency count and mean (\bar{X}) was used to analyze data generated on research questions, while, inferential statistics Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC).

Presentation of Findings and Discussion of Results.

Presentation of Findings

Research Question one: Can vocational skills Acquisition program equip people with skills to promote local technology Ondo State, Nigeria?

Table I: Showing simple percentages, Frequency counts and mean (\bar{X}) On can vocational acquisition programme. Equip people will skills to promote local technology in Ondo State, Nigeria.

		N= 1,080				C = 2.5			
S/N	ITEMS	SA %	A %	D %	SD %	N	Mean(\bar{X})	Decision	
1	The programme offers skills on vocations that will help to embark on local technology	896 82.96	156 14.44	24 2.22	4 0.37	1,080	3.80	Accepted	
2	Skill acquired through the programme have no relevance to local technology	898 83.14	89 8.24	69 6.38	24 2.22	1,080	4.02	Accepted	
3	The programme mainly offer vocational skills that focus mainly on production of local materials	883 81.75	124 11.48	64 5.92	9 0.83	1,080	4.04	Accepted	
4	Apart from production of local materials skills offered by the programme can also be used for more section of technology	932 85.46	96 8.88	52 4.81	9 0.83	1,080	4.09	Accepted	
5	The programme do not offer modern day skills for adoption of local technology	5 0.46	12 1.11	97 8.89	966 89.44	1,080	1.43	Rejected	
6	Absolute vocational skills are being offered	6 0.55	11 1.01	103 9.53	960 88.88	1,080	1.22	Rejected	

	thus, could not enhance adoption of local technology							
	TOTAL WEIGHT	3,611 55.81%	478 7.38%	409 6.32%	1,972 30.47%		2.93	Accepted

KEYS: N = Number of Respondents C = Cut of point, \bar{X} = Mean, SA = strongly agreed, A = Agreed, D = Disagreed, SD = Strongly disagreed

Source: Field survey, 2024

Table 1 above, shows the respondents response for research question one. Items 1, shows the following responses; 896 (82.96), 156 (14.44), 24 (2.22) and 4 (0.37) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed. On item 2, responses obtained indicated 898 (83.14), 89 (8.24), 69 (6.38) and 24 (2.22) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed, strongly disagreed. On item 3, the responses got were; 883 (81.75), 124 (11.48), 64 (5.92) and 9 (0.83) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed, strongly disagreed, respectively.

On item 4, the following responses were got; 924 (85.46), 96 (8.88), 52 (4.81) and 9 (0.83) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed, strongly disagreed. On item 5, responses obtained also revealed 5 (0.46), 12 (1.11), 97 (8.98) and 966 (89.44) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed, strongly disagreed. Finally item 6 shows the following responses, 6 (0.55), 11 (1.01), 103 (9.53) and 960 (88.88) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed, strongly disagreed.

Generally speaking, the avenue rating scale of four $\bar{X} = 2.5$ is lesser than the mean of average ratings scale of four $\bar{X} = 2.93$, thus, indicated that vocational skill acquisition programme could enhance the adoption of local technology.

Research Question two: Can entrepreneurial skills acquisition programme enhance people with skills for local technology development in Ondo state, Nigeria.

Table 2: Showing simple percentages, frequently counts, mean(\bar{X}) on can entrepreneurial skills acquisition programme enhance people with skills for local technology development in Ondo State, Nigeria?

N = 1.080 C = 2.5								
S/N	ITEMS	SD %	A %	D %	SD %	N	Mean(\bar{X})	Decision
7	ESAP do offer appropriate skills that can promote local technology	23 2.12	35 3.24	125 11.57	897 83.05	1,080	1.34	Rejected
8	ESAP skills that are being	933 86.38	46 4.25	69 6.38	32 2.96	1,080	4.04	Accepted

	offering are not directly relevant to local technology							
9	ESAP is mainly to enhance people with vocational skills for adoption of local technology	33 3.05	21 1.94	114 10.55	912 84.44	1,080	1.33	Rejected
10	Adoption of local technology is not a major foal of ESAP	889 82.31	121 11.20	48 4.44	222.03	1,080	4.03	Accepted
11	ESAP offers skills on business development rather than promoting local production of materials	836 77.40	159 14.72	63 5.83	22 2.03	1,080	3.95	Accepted
12	ESAP is relevant to local technology development	33 3.05	56 5.18	69 6.38	922 85.37	1,080	1.36	Rejected
	TOTAL WEIGHT	2,747 42.39%	438 6.75%	488 7.53%	2,807 43.31%		2.67	Accepted

KEYS: N = Number of respondents, C = cut of f points, X = mean, SA = Strongly Agreed, A = Agreed, D = Disagreed, SD = Strongly Disagreed

Source: Field survey, 2024

Table 2 above, shows the respondents response on research question two. On item 7, 23 (2.12), 35 (3.24), 125 (11.57) and 897 (83.05) response were obtained for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed, strongly disagreed. On item 8, the following response were got: 933 (86.38), 46 (4.25), 69 (6.38) and 32 (2.96) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed, strongly disagreed. On item 9, 33 (3.05), 21 (1.94), 114 (10.55) and 912 (84.44) response were obtained for strongly agree, agree, disagreed, strongly disagreed, respectively. On item 10, 899 (82.31), 121 (11.20), 48 (4.44) and 22 (2.03) response were got for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed, strongly disagreed. On item 11, the following response were got; 836 (77.40), 159 (14.72), 63 (5.83) and 22 (2.03) for strongly agree, agreed, disagreed, strongly disagreed.

Received: 13 February 2025

Revised: 22 February 2025

Accepted: 3 March 2025

Copyright © authors 2025

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14975143>

Finally, on item 12, response obtained were; 33 (3.05), 56 (5.18), 69 (6.38) and 922 (85.37) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed, strongly disagreed.

On a several note, the average rating of four X = 2.5 is lesser than the mean of average rating scale of four X = 2.67

Research Hypothesis

H01: There will be no significant relationship between vocational and entrepreneurial skill acquisition programme impact on local technology promotion in Ondo State, Nigeria.

Table 3: (PPMCC) showing the relationship between vocational and entrepreneurial impact on local technological promotion in Ondo State, Nigeria.

Variables	Mean (\bar{X})	Std. Dev.	N	R	P	REMARK
Vocational Skills Acquisition Programme (VSAP)	14.5157	1.5847	1,080	.366*	.000	Sis
Entrepreneurial Skills Acquisition Programme (ESAP)	16.8123	1.7252	1,080	.016*	.075	Not Sis
Promotion of Local Technology (PLT)	18.1278	2.1865				

***Significant at 0.5 Level**

Table 3 above shows that there is a positive significant relationship between VSAP and promotion of local technology (PLT). Hence, (r = .366*, N= 1,080, P<.0.5) thus, null hypothesis, rejected. In contrary, ESAP did not. Hence, (r =.016*, N = 1,080, P>.0.5. Null hypothesis accepted.

Discussion of Results

The result on research question one indicated that local technology could be promoted through Vocational Skill Acquisition Programme (VSAP). The result aligns with the opinion of Thioglobulem (1992) and Nnaka and Amachile (2011), that the technological sector of nations could be developed through effective planning of Vocational Skill Acquisition Programme. Nneji (1992), further corroborated the result that, VSAP is an impetus for promotion and adoption of local technology. Erinsakin (2014), submission also buttress the results that VSAP could speed up the rate at which people venture into production of materials using local technology.

The result on research question two shows that Entrepreneurial Skill Acquisition Programme (ESAP) could enhance people with skills for development of local technology. The

result is corroborated by Agagu (2007) that implementation of ESAP is implemented to bring revolution to utilization of local materials for the production of goods and services for man use.

On the research hypothesis of the study as indicated on table 3. Scholars opinions affirmed that VSAP could bring about local technological revolution. Nwogu (1988), stated firmly that in Nigeria to enhance the adoption of local technology, education system needs to be refocused on acquisition of practical vocational skills. However, the result shows that Entrepreneurial Skill Acquisition Programme could not promote practicing local technology.

Conclusion

Premised on the results obtained on the research questions and hypothesis, conclusions were local technology adoption and practices could be promoted through VSAP. However, the result of research hypothesis shows a contrary position for ESAP, thus, it did not have most impact on local technological revolution.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the conclusion of the study:

1. Enough resources should be committed to Vocational and Entrepreneurial Skills Acquisition Programme by Ondo State Government.
2. Public should be sensitized through the print and electronic media on the relevance of the programme to adoption and practice of VESAP
3. More centres of VESAP should be created to enable people to have access to the programme
4. VESAP should be well planned and monitored by its provider(s).
5. Government should synergize efforts with international agencies and organizations for effective implementation of the programme.
6. The graduates of VESAP should be mobilized with capital to enable them put skills acquired through the programme into practice and so on.

References

- Agagu, O.K (2007). A speech presented at graduation ceremony and presentation of certificates of proficiency and distribution of cheque to graduates of skill acquisition programme in Ondo State on 26th February, 2007.
- Becker, G.S. (1964, 1963 & 1996). *Human Capital*. New York: Columbia University Press.
- Eke, H.N, Igwesi, U & Orji, D.J. (2011). Information professionals as agent for promoting entrepreneurship and technology education in actualizing vision 2020 for Nigeria.

- Ezeji, U.E & Okone, A. (1999).The relevance of business studies.A conference paper presented at the international submit held in Port-Harcourt, 6th – 9th June, 1999.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2004).National policy on education, Lagos: NERDC.
- Nwogu, B.G. (1988). The instructional system : An innovation in instructional technology in Oyejemezi, D.A (ed). Educational Technology in Nigeria. Onisha: Summer Educational.
- Nnaka, C.R & Amachile, S. (2011). Skill acquisition : Importance for business studies educators among secondary schools in River State. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Science*, 2:7
- Thiegbulum, O.T. (1992). Academic performance of Nigeria certificate in education (technical) students with different entry requirement : A case study of Federal College of Education (Technical, Omoku, Rivers State). *Journal of Technical Teachers Education*, 1.1 : 14-24.
- Uwameiye, R. (2011). Vocational and technical education : A synergy presented at 4th Annual national conference of school of vocational and technical education, Adeyemi College of Education, Ondo, November 1st – 4th.
- Gambari, J. (2011). The importance of skills acquisition : A challenge to Nigeria Legislators. www.nasslegisdigestonline.com. Retrieved September 22nd.
- Nnenji, E.A. (1992). Redirection of technology education curriculum for solid foundation for technology education. A paper presented at the 6th Annual Conference of the Nigerian Association of Teachers of Technology, Akoka, Lagos.
- Matammi, S & Awodun, M. (2005).An assessment of comparative strategies and growth patterns of new enterprises in Nigeria using the developing economy model.*Lagos Organization Review*, 1.1 : 26-32.
- Benchard, N. & Toulouse, B. (1988).The impact of finance of small enterprises in developing countries, London : Oxford University Press.
- Salami, C.G.E (2011). Entrepreneurship and youth unemployment in Nigeria : The missing link. *Global Journal of management and Business Research*, 11.5 : 18-25.
- Ogundele, O.J.K. (2000). Determinants of entrepreneurial emergence, behaviour and performance in Nigeria. Unpublished Ph.D thesis, University of Lagos : Akoka.
- Erinsakin, M.O. (2014).Impact evaluation of skill acquisition and entrepreneurial development training programme in Ondo State, Nigeria.